

Chelation in Relation to Iron Mobilization and Phosphate Availability in Soil*

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A comparative study of iron mobilization and consequent release of phosphate by three pure chelating agents from two major types of West Bengal soils at different pH, has been carried out. Irrespective of the soils the order of chelating ability of pure compounds has been found to be succinic acid > phloroglucinol > glutamic acid in the major part of pH-range.

THE role of organic matter both in pedogenesis and in soil fertility, is well characterised. Apart from that, its capacity to form stable complexes with many of the polyvalent ions, has drawn a considerable part of attention in particular. The thorough study of Kononova¹ reveals the presence of many imino, amino, carboxyl, hydroxy etc. groups in soil organic matter which may take part in chelation. Bloomfield^{2,3,4}, Muir *et al.*^{5,6} and Coulson *et al.*^{7,8} have already pointed out that the presence of polyphenols, amino acids and other organic acids is responsible for the mobilization of iron.

In the present investigation, we have studied the effect of three reagents, representing three important groups generally involved in the chelation process, such as amino acids, polycarboxyl acids and polyphenols on the mobilization of iron and the consequent release of phosphate in two major types of Bengal soil.

Material and Methods

Soils :

The alluvial soil (designated as C-soil) was collected from a paddy field of Chakdah, district Nadia and irrigated by deep tube well water. The occurrence of a brown incrustation on the soil in drought period is reported.

The red soil (R-soil) was collected from the district of Purulia from an uncultivated upland field. Both the soils were air-dried, ground and passed through 80-mesh sieve, prior to any experiment.

The important properties of both the soil samples are given in Table 1.

Reagents :

The three representative chelating agents, phloroglucinol; glutamic acid and succinic acid and also all other reagents and chemicals used in this investigation were of analar grade.

Apparatus :

A systronics pH-meter fitted with glass and calomel electrodes and a Beckmann colorimeter were used for the measurements of pH and absorbances respectively, of the experimental solutions.

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS UNDER INVESTIGATION

No. of experiment	Properties	Purulia soil (R-soil)	Chakdah soil (C-soil)
1.	Moisture percentage	3.52	4.68
2.	Soil pH (1 : 2.5 ratio)	5.90	6.30
3.	Available phosphorus (mg/100g) (Bray)	0.24	0.51
4.	Nitrogen (%)	0.06	0.09
5.	Organic Carbon (%)	0.92	1.06
6.	Total Iron (%)	6.80	5.20
7.	Total Calcium (%)	0.63	2.10
8.	Free Iron Oxides (Fe %)	2.80	1.51
9.	Exchangeable Ferrous, Ferric and slightly acid soluble Iron (mg/100 g)	0.68	0.32

Methods :

The standard colorimetric methods such as, O-phenanthroline and sulphomolybdic acid-stannous chloride, were used in this study for the determination of iron and phosphate respectively.

Experimental

A saturation solution of phloroglucinol was prepared in warm water and the percentage in solution was determined to be 0.753. The glutamic acid and

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succinic acid were also dissolved in water so as to give the same molar concentration.

A 10g of the soil was weighed out in specimen tubes; 5 ml of (N) acetic acid and 15 ml of the prepared solution were added and the pH of the tubes were adjusted from 3 to 9 with the help of fractional pH-paper by adding 1(N) HCl or 2(N) NaOH as required. During the incubation period the tubes were stored in dark, to avoid any photochemical decomposition of the constituents.

After 36 hr of incubation, the suspensions were filtered on Whatman No. 42 filter paper under reduced pressure. No washing was done. The equilibrium pH-values of the filtrate were recorded with pH-meter. The filtrates were then oxidised at hot condition with the mixture of concentration H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ to break the chelated complexes and to decompose the residual organic matter. The residual liquids were then transferred into a 50-ml volumetric flask and made upto volume with distilled water. Iron and phosphorus were established colorimetrically by taking appropriate aliquots from the above stocks.

The results are shown in Tables 2, 3 and 4 and also presented graphically in Figures 1 and 2.

Earlier it was observed^{9,10} that submergence has no appreciable effect on the solubilization of iron in first two to three days. On submergence complete reduction of nitrate and partly that of manganese

which takes 2 to 3 days, initiates the reduction process of iron. Accordingly, no control experiment was conducted since it was assumed that simple submergence with water would not contribute anything to the values for soluble iron and phosphate obtained after 36 hr. of incubation.

TABLE 2—MOBILIZATION OF IRON AND PHOSPHORUS WITH PHLOROGLUCINOL AFTER 36 HR. OF INCUBATION

C-Soil			R-Soil		
pH	Fe-mg/100g	P-mg/100g	pH	Fe-mg/100g	P-mg/100g
3.05	1.19	0.15	3.60	1.58	0.10
4.00	1.75	0.13	4.00	1.48	0.12
4.90	1.47	0.08	5.05	1.24	0.09
5.50	1.16	0.20	5.60	1.09	0.17
7.10	1.28	0.45	7.30	1.16	0.28
9.20	1.16	0.45	9.40	1.13	0.28

TABLE 3—MOBILIZATION OF IRON AND PHOSPHORUS WITH GLUTAMIC ACID AFTER 36 HR. OF INCUBATION

C-Soil			R-Soil		
pH	Fe-mg/100g	P-mg/100g	pH	Fe-mg/100g	P-mg/100g
3.20	0.73	0.15	3.20	0.34	0.09
4.00	0.79	0.15	4.00	0.78	0.08
5.00	0.49	0.10	5.10	0.69	0.08
5.00	0.60	0.16	5.60	0.43	0.06
8.60	0.83	0.09	7.90	0.60	0.14
9.20	0.87	0.19	9.90	0.73	0.15

Fig. 1. Effect of chelating agents on the release of iron.

- ▲ — Succinic acid.
- — Phloroglucinol
- — Glutamic acid
- R-soil
- C-soil.

Results and Discussion

From the Fig. 1, it is apparent that chelating ability of phloroglucinol steadily diminished after pH 4.0; this is in conformity with the observation of earlier investigators who reported that the polyphenols transport iron in ferrous state at a lower⁸ pH.

TABLE 4—MOBILIZATION OF IRON AND PHOSPHORUS WITH SUCCINIC ACID AFTER 36 HR. OF INCUBATION

C-Soil			R-Soil		
pH	Fe-mg/ 100g	P-mg/ 100g	pH	Fe-mg/ 100g	P-mg/ 100g
2.90	2.25	0.71	3.00	1.47	0.19
3.90	1.00	0.46	4.10	1.03	0.24
4.90	0.95	0.72	5.00	2.00	0.35
5.80	0.73	0.39	5.90	2.00	0.28
8.00	1.78	0.25	7.50	2.70	0.45
9.10	0.74	0.30	9.70	1.50	0.40

The study reveals that although both phloroglucinol and glutamic acid transport iron at a lower pH, the comparative release is much higher in the case of former. Moreover, the presence of a secondary complex of glutamic acid is indicated at pH 8.0. It is possibly due to greater co-ordinating capacity of carboxyl group, i.e., greater stability of the iron chelate at a higher pH. The earlier workers⁶, however, reported that the amino acids become inactive above pH 4.5.

Fig. 2. Effect of pure chelating agents on the release of phosphate

▲ — Succinic acid
● — Phloroglucinol
■ — Glutamic acid
— C-Soil
- - - R-Soil.

Among the three organic compounds studied, succinic acid reveals its quite distinctive feature with respect to the other two. Apart from its greater release of iron throughout the entire range of pH under investigation, the release curve shows a maxima at pH 8.0, where the other two become practically inactive. Muir, *et al.*⁶ also obtained similar results. Their organic acid fraction was capable to keep iron in solution from pH 4.0 to pH 9.5, with a highest value at pH 8.0. Values obtained in the present investigation as evident from the Figures 1 are also in conformity with their results.

In soils under investigation, the native phosphates are present mostly in organic forms. In the cultivated soil, it is likely that iron and aluminium phosphates occur in thin films, for which chelation reaction was better manifested.

From the above study it is quite apparent that among the three reagents used, succinic acid is most effective in solubilizing phosphates from both the soils (Fig. 2).

From Fig. 2 it is obvious that increase in phosphate concentration at higher pH with phloroglucinol and glutamic acid is not due to the chelation of iron since the solubilizing action of these anions on iron is significant only at lower pH values (Fig. 1). It is due to probable exchange of phosphate with OH⁻ ions which is dominant at higher pH-range. The chelation of calcium may also be taken in consideration for this higher availability of phosphates at higher pH-range.

With succinic acid, maximum release of iron are obtained at pH 8.0 and pH 7.5 for the C-Soil and R-Soil respectively. The point of maximum mobilization of iron at pH 7.5 in red soil can be correlated with the point of maximum release of phosphate at the same pH. On the other hand, it is quite interesting, the point of maximum mobilization of iron at pH 8.0 in C-Soil corresponds to minimum phosphate availability. The higher content of calcium in this soil, which can fix phosphate more effectively at this pH, may be one of the causes; or it is quite possible that the conjugate action of the applied anion and OH⁻ present in solution is rather incapable in keeping phosphate ions in solution phase.

The general order of chelating ability as evident from the amount of iron mobilized in solution phase is found to be succinic acid > phloroglucinol > glutamic acid.

The application of micronutrients to deficient plants as a chelated complex is a recent trend. The present study may offer a possible guideline in selecting an appropriate chelating agent for the above purpose. The mechanism of interaction of organic matter with the metallic constituents of soil is also partly understood in the light of the above study on chelation.

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